

Esterification of Methanol with a Homologous Series of Acids Using Amberlite IR-120

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The esterification of methanol with a homologous series of aliphatic organic acids such as formic, acetic, propionic, butyric and valeric in presence of Amberlite IR-120 (H⁺ form) as a catalyst was studied. The effect of the structure of reactant has been investigated by application of Taft's equation.

THE position of final equilibrium in the esterification reaction is usually not very dependent on the alkyl group. On the other hand, the rate of reaction is strongly dependent on the size of alkyl group of acid and alcohol.

The effect of structure was studied¹ using different alcohols. The reaction rate was found to decrease by increasing the alcohol chain length or its branching.

The esterification of amyl and isoamyl alcohol with propionic and butyric acid was studied². It was concluded that the rate of reaction decreased with increasing the branching of the side chain of both alcohol and acid due to the steric hindrance.

The same conclusion was established³ for esterifying ethanol with acetic and isobutyric acids in presence of cation exchanger.

Experimental

BDH (AnalaR) chemicals were used. The cation exchanger employed was Amberlite IR-120 with capacity 6.84 meq/g and mesh size 14-52 m μ with 8% crosslinkage. The catalyst was regenerated and dried before use.

The reaction was carried out in a three-necked flask, the reactants were charged through one neck. A spiral condenser fitted into the second neck and the third neck was used for withdrawing samples via a glass tube reaching under the surface of the reaction mixture to avoid any leakage of vapour.

The calculated amount of resin, equivalent to 20.857 meq of H⁺ ion was soaked in methanol overnight, then heated up to the required temperature with constant stirring for one hour before starting the experiment. Zero time was recorded when the organic acid was added. The unreacted acid was determined potentiometrically at intervals.

Results and Discussion

Esterification of methanol with a homologous series of acids such as formic, acetic, propionic,

butyric and valeric in presence of Amberlite IR-120 as a catalyst was studied. The experimental results obtained are shown in Table 1.

TABLE 1—ESTERIFICATION OF METHANOL WITH DIFFERENT ORGANIC ACIDS

No.	Acid	Temp. °C	x_e	$k_1 \cdot 10^6$		ΔE k cal	K
				Found	Calcd.		
1	Formic	60	0.9643	22.0843	22.1534		1.85574
2	"	47	0.9592	13.0510	13.2843		1.60604
3	"	42	0.9565	10.3257	10.7904	8.300	1.49760
4	"	37	0.9538	6.7478	8.7060		1.40186
5	Acetic	60	0.9630	4.2692	4.2734		1.78555
6	"	55	0.9510	3.4587	3.4399		1.68671
7	"	50	0.9590	2.6836	2.7503	9.385	1.59552
8	"	44	0.9568	2.1186	2.1837		1.50898
9	Propionic	60	0.9602	2.4985	2.3472		1.64994
10	"	55	0.9584	1.9783	1.8724		1.57246
11	"	50	0.9560	1.5363	1.4830	9.780	1.47898
12	"	45	0.9535	1.1672	1.1661		1.39193
13	Butyric	60	0.9564	1.3276	1.3192		1.49383
14	"	55	0.9546	1.0712	1.0430		1.42906
15	"	50	0.9523	0.8174	0.8187	10.160	1.35337
16	"	45	0.9498	0.6373	0.6377		1.27900
17	Valeric	60	0.9514	0.9876	0.8961		1.32571
18	"	55	0.9497	0.6863	0.7043		1.27619
19	"	50	0.9472	0.5555	0.5495	10.415	1.20916
20	"	45	0.9440	0.4386	0.4253		1.13211

$$a = 1.6462 \text{ (gm mol l}^{-1}\text{)},$$

$$B(\text{molar ratio}) = 15.00,$$

$$W = 4.74 \text{ (g catalyst/100 g reactants)},$$

$$\text{Resin capacity} = 6.84 \text{ meq/g.}$$

An excess of methanol was used and the amount of acid taken was to give a constant molar ratio of alcohol/acid = 15.00. The amount of catalyst employed in all experiments was kept constant. All experiments were thermostated and stirred at the same stirring rate.

The value of the reaction velocity constant was obtained using the following rate expression.

$$r = k_1 (a - x) (b - x) - k_2 x^2 \quad \dots (1)$$

The more general form of this expression could be deduced to be

$$k_1 = \frac{1}{t} \frac{x_0^2}{(a+b)x_0 - ab} \frac{1}{m_1 - x_0} \ln \frac{m_1 - x x_0}{x_0 - x m_1} \dots (2)$$

where, $m_1 = B - x_0$ and $B = \frac{x_0^2(a+b)}{(a+b)x_0 - ab}$

In all cases the value of k_1 was calculated using the kinetic expression represented by equation (2).

Plotting $\ln \frac{m_1 - x x_0}{x_0 - x m_1} \cdot \frac{x_0}{m_1}$ against time gives good straight lines showing that the esterification of methanol with the organic acids under investigation is a second order reversible reaction.

Assuming that the amount of catalyst and molar ratio have no effect on the activation energy, a correlation representing the effect of the H^+ ion concentration (meq/reactants) on the reaction velocity constant is given by

$$k_1 = \frac{B}{W} \text{ meq } e^{-\Delta E/RT} \dots (3)$$

According to this equation the value of k_1 could be calculated.

The reaction velocity constant decreases with increase in size of the alkyl group, the rate of decrease gradually diminishes with increase in size of alkyl group. This depression may be attributed to two reasons :

(i) The decrease of pore diffusion with increase in the alkyl group $^{\alpha-\sigma}$ —this factor is diminished by the higher rate of stirring and swelling of the resin in methanol before use.

(ii) The operation of steric hindrance and inductive effect of the alkyl group attached to the acid molecule.

The latter suggestion may be tested using Taft's equation^r. Drawing $\ln k_1/k_{CH_3}$ for different acids vs the polar factor (σ^*) a broken line is obtained (Fig. 1). The first part of the line includes formic, acetic and propionic acids and the second includes propionic, butyric and valeric acids. It is evident that in the first part the inductive effect has a slight effect on the reaction rate.

Following this sequence of acids the polar factor gradually increases and the rate of reaction consequently decreases. A large difference appears between the behaviour of formic and acetic, while a slight difference can be observed between acetic and propionic acids. Thus, the alkyl group in acetic acid causes a decrease in the reactivity of acetic acid in comparison to formic. Propionic acid is largely affected by the inductive effect of its alkyl group due to the increase in electron deficiency on the α -carbon atom adjacent to carboxylic group. Thus the polar factor has a small effect on the rate of esterification of formic and acetic acids.

Fig. 1. Taft's correlation for the esterification of different acids with methanol.

Fig. 2. Taft's correlation for the esterification of different acids with methanol.

In the second part of the curve, σ^* affects to a large extent the rate of esterifying propionic, butyric and valeric acids. Thus, σ^* exerted by the alkyl group influences largely the α -carbon atom.

Steric factor (E_s) has been studied by application of Taft's equation (Fig. 2). This factor has a slight effect on the reaction rate of the acids under investigation, but in case of formic acid it decreases greatly in comparison to these acids. This is due to the fact that formic acid has no bulky alkyl group, whose presence may restrict the acid molecule to approach the alcohol molecule. It can also hinder the acid molecule to approach the active sites of the catalyst.

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